

CURRENT TRENDS IN MODERN BRIDGE CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract: The article discusses current problems of modern bridge construction, trends in the development of bridge construction, problems in the operation of bridges.

Key words: bridge construction, dynamic loads, optimal design, cable-stayed system.

Introduction. The construction of bridges is not only the process of constructing a structure, but it is also a scientific and technical activity that is aimed at finding new technologies and materials. The construction and reconstruction of bridges is one of the most complex types of construction. The peculiarity of bridge construction is that almost each of them is unique [1, 2]. Many modern bridges are monuments of engineering art and have long been part of city architecture. The construction of bridges is carried out taking into account the characteristics of the terrain, therefore, complex calculations are required for each of the bridge structures, taking into account the characteristics of the soil, loads and a number of other complex parameters. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the possible increase in traffic intensity and the effect of environmental factors [5, 7].

The article describes modern bridge construction technologies, and also identifies problems of modern bridge construction, including: emergency situations during the construction, operation and dismantling of bridges, emergency situations during the construction or at the beginning of operation of bridges, construction unfinished for many years, minor local damage to bridges during construction,

problems with financing, as well as a decrease in the qualifications of bridge builders and designers [3, 4, 6].

The construction of bridges requires the participation of professionals who can ensure not only the safety of bridge construction, but also the necessary reliability of the structures.

To build a bridge, it is necessary to answer a number of questions: what type of bridge to choose, what materials will be used, what will be the design of the bridge and the technology of its construction. It is also important to consider the location of the future bridge to ensure its safety and quality [7, 8, 9].

The design and construction of bridges, especially long ones, is a complex and expensive process that takes several years and includes a significant amount of construction and installation work. Modern bridge construction technologies and super-strong building structures make it possible to erect structures of any shape and size, both in cities and towns, and in the most inaccessible places [10, 11, 12].

The construction of the bridge begins with engineering surveys and development of design documentation. Thanks to modern technologies, using special software systems, design time can be significantly reduced. And the experience of specialists allows us to select the most effective technological solutions for the construction of bridges, to reduce the time and cost of construction, taking into account the capabilities of the manufacturer and installation organization [13, 14].

When developing a plan for the construction of a bridge structure, depending on the type of bridge, the depth, the structure of the soil in different states, climatic features, features of vegetation cover, the possibility of flooding, the possibility of deformation of the riverbed, etc. are taken into account.

The construction of bridges necessarily includes the following stages: preparatory work, erection of formwork, reinforcement, pouring concrete, concrete care and final activities.

The preparatory work includes both comprehensive surveys and various measurements, the creation of an embankment, etc. Off-site preparatory work

includes: road construction, laying utility networks and erecting engineering structures, blasting in quarries and dumps, and creating other infrastructure. On-site work includes: installation of a geodetic base, cleaning of the construction area, pumping out water, transfer of transit communications and installation of main on-site utility networks, environmental monitoring, fencing and lighting.

The next stage is the construction of supports. The choice of support design usually depends on the height of the supports, the design of the spans, the purpose of the structure, and the load level. But not unimportant factors are hydrological conditions (the nature of the water flow under the bridge) and geological conditions. Based on the method of construction, support structures are divided into three typical types: prefabricated, monolithic and prefabricated monolithic. Each method of constructing support structures has its own laying order.

The problem of increasing construction volumes and increasing complexity of objects, including the development of underground space and dense urban development, has set construction science the task of optimal design and reliable operation of construction projects, in particular, such complex building structures as bridges.

Primitive bridges, which consisted of a log thrown over a stream, arose in ancient times. Later, stone was used as a building material.

Since the end of the 18th century, metal has been used for construction. In the 19th century, the advent of railways required the creation of bridges capable of withstanding significant loads, which stimulated the development of bridge construction.

As a rule, bridges consist of spans and supports. Superstructures serve to carry loads and transfer them to supports. The first (and most expensive - up to 50% of the total cost of construction) stage in building a bridge is the construction of supports. Span structures are usually installed on supports using erection cranes.

During the construction and operation of bridges, mistakes and miscalculations often occur, which lead to accidents and disasters. The cause of spontaneous bridge

collapse may be its improper design. When creating a bridge design, you should always take into account possible natural disasters, such as strong winds or earthquakes. In the 19th and early 20th centuries, several bridge failures occurred due to the resonance that the bridge experienced when troops passed over it. When the frequency of external influence (soldiers step in step) coincides with the natural frequency of vibrations of the bridge, a sharp increase in the amplitude of vibrations of the bridge occurs, and the bridge structure cannot withstand this. Due to the resonance, the following collapsed: the Angers Bridge, the Egyptian Bridge (St. Petersburg 1905), the Tacoma Bridge (USA, 1940).

Bridges as structures operate under dynamic loading conditions, including heavy loads.

To create reliable methods for mobile determination of defects and damage in structures and prompt decision-making for their elimination, dynamic testing of structures with computer modeling is carried out. Currently, a technique for continuous dynamic (and static) monitoring of changes in the stress-strain state of structures has been developed and successfully applied. This technique was used, for example, in the construction of a new cable-stayed bridge in Vladivostok to Russky Island [1].

The bridge to Russky Island in Vladivostok is one of the largest cable-stayed bridges in the world. The new bridge passes through the Eastern Bosphorus Strait and connects the mainland with Russky Island. This is the first bridge of this size and design in Russia. It can rightfully be called a unique achievement of Russian engineers, since the bridge became a record holder in several respects at once: the longest cable-stayed span in the world (1104 m), the longest cable-stayed span (580 m). In addition, it took second place in the world in height, its pylons reach a height of 320 m. The total length of the structure is 3100 m, and the height of the main canvas is 70 m above the ground, which allows even the most bulky ocean liners to pass under it.

The cable-stayed system is, without exaggeration, the basis of the bridge. It is she who takes on the main static and dynamic loads; without it, the existence of the bridge is simply not possible. For a bridge to be strong, the cable stays must be maximally protected from the effects of natural elements and other adverse factors. The massive structure of the bridge across the Eastern Bosphorus Strait is held in place by 168 cable stays, ranging from 135 to 579 m in length. They have the highest levels of endurance, strength, and corrosion resistance, which, according to experts, ensured an estimated service life of at least 100 years. The structure is capable of withstanding a tensile load equal to 1850 MPa.

Due to the fact that the compact configuration of the cables has a shell of smaller diameter, it was possible to reduce the wind load on the bridge by 25-30%. In addition, this technology made it possible to reduce by a third the cost of materials for the construction of foundations, stiffening beams and pylons. In addition, the installed cables have a vibration damping system, which allows them to stabilize the structure in strong winds.

The cable stays were attached to the pylons after strengthening the foundation and was carried out at a height of 189 m. Modern technology was also used here, which made it possible to significantly speed up the construction - concreting the pylon body and installing the cable-stayed pairs were carried out simultaneously. But still, the longest cable-stayed bridge in the world is still located in China. The length of the Hangzhou Bay Bridge in the East China Sea is about 36 km, which is almost 18 times longer than the new Far East Bridge. Its construction cost China \$1.4 billion. The bridge is located in an area with difficult climatic conditions, where there are often typhoons, storms and squally winds. Because of this, the bridge structure was specially strengthened and a special composition of concrete and steel was used for construction, which is resistant to typhoons. The commissioning of this bridge is also important from both economic and social points of view. Since it opens up new opportunities for the development of both Vladivostok and the entire Far Eastern region.

By building this bridge, Russia actually proved to the entire world community that it can independently implement large and complex projects from an engineering point of view. After all, all stages of the project from the design stage to construction were carried out entirely by Russian specialists.

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